

THE FUTURE TEACHERS' ROLE IN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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“A good teacher is like a candle it consumes itself to light the way for others.”

Mustafa Kemal Atatürk.

ABSTRACT

In this article, there is being demonstrated several foreign countries teaching system and their teachers' significant role in their Education system of European countries; the UK and American countries; the United States. As well as that our traditional teaching system in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its developing modern teaching system among the upcoming teachers in country. Correspondingly, what kind of educational differences between the foreign countries and the Republic of Uzbekistan, differing from teaching system in high schools, as well. Typically, which abilities demanding to be a good teacher, simply stated that the well-qualified instructors are the future generation of our current education system as opposed to our older generation used methods in education system. Furthermore, there will be discussed about the amount of salary of teachers should be in higher prices as financial support because that they are giving energy to teach young teachers in high schools, especially in pedagogy field.

Key words: *teaching system, education system, European countries, USA educational theories, traditional teaching system, Uzbekistan developing education system, future generations, future teachers, financial benefits, Pedagogical theory.*

In this world, there are countries like America and the United Kingdom which are well-developed countries, in the case of, educational theories in their universities. Mostly, the international students of European countries are mentally stronger than any other country, to clearly define that the individuals of foreign universities can study better and get their qualifications easily in social works. Additionally, the students who study abroad can get well-paid jobs easily, in public theory, and so, this thought commonly lead our national students to study in foreign countries, including: the USA, the UK, Finland, Poland, Russian and Japan. Admittedly, the teaching system in high schools of foreign universities has more merits rather than studying in national areas. Honestly, our education system need more intellectual citizens, so nowadays, our president: Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, has recently organized meeting with the president of America: Joe Biden, over the 5 Asian countries' presidential performance contained. Altogether, our future education system is up to our young teachers who teach future generations in Uzbekistan.

Even, mentioned in quote of Nelson Mandela: “Education is the most powerful weapon you can use to change the world.” Education is our greatest opportunity to give an irrevocable gift to the next generation. We need to teach the next generation of children from day one that they are responsible for their lives. Mankind's greatest gift, also its greatest curse, is that we have free choice. Clearly, every successful position will be achieved by learning how to deal with solutions, not focusing on issues.

From my perspective as a future teacher, every teacher must educate the students from their heart. Purely, in example of having positivity about the environment of studying, including several most demanding capabilities: significant soft skills; time management skills, leadership skills, having a strong work ethic, problem solving abilities, high emotional intelligence, and possessing the knowledge and adaptability needed to employ a variety of teaching modes and methods. On the condition that, if teachers can't handle with their jobs, the students also grow weak-minded as it is harmful for our education system. Mainly, in every dilemma about

educating students depends on well-educated teachers, at first. Then, there might be no other issues in order to learn how to study well, except the salary of educators and apart from students' mindset.

“Both fools and smart people are beautiful, but only half-fools and weak-minded people are harmful.” - I. Goethe. In the international bestseller book of James Clear named ‘Atomic Habits’ mentioned about marvelous consequences by in hint of changing actions. In this book, he explains widely available methods to build amazing habits by breaking evil behaviors. [1] To clear that for the purpose of having a good personality and becoming the best self-teaching studios, students should read the book for the room improvement of their mind. Coupled with, any students can come across with local libraries to find a great condition to educate themselves as government operationally constructed it. With this in mind, students can find books about, consisting of, pedagogy, science and education, especially in old books, published in around 1990-1995. In that books written widely explanation for being well-qualified instructors. Importantly, books tell more information about everything related to teaching, studying and even the Samarkand State Institute of foreign languages' high-educated teachers would recommend to work on ourselves in terms of being aware of all the ancestors used methodology and Pedagogy. From the book named ‘Pedagogy’ published in 1990, that there explicitly stated about young teachers who are LITTLE BREAKERS: “If there is only one tape recorder, it is assigned to a student of the parallel class to listen to the recordings on it outside of class. This honor work is entrusted to good students only once during the academic term. The time of consumption is 15-20 minutes. If there are two tape recorders, the students of the parallel class will listen to the recordings during the lesson when the written work is canceled. On such a day, students will be given "five automatic grades" for written work, which are different from the grades given on the information sheet, which clearly shows the grade of knowledge. Sometimes the teacher listens to some notes. Experience has shown that children are very strict judges, and in all the years it has never been observed that they have been liberal with

the mistakes of their siblings.” And, it is just a peace of knowledge from huge theories.

When it comes to teachers' salary that I can fearlessly convey about the increasing the amount of income. Nowadays, government is solving the issue about financial benefits for teachers in association with the other fields like; doctors, especially in nursing health insurance, retired professionals. As folks can see, in schools as well as in higher education, the teachers ask for requirements to pay higher income that is the reason why, teachers need also financial benefits for their family members, offsprings, for their health problems as educating pupils requiring more energetic mood to teach well. For this situation, only if teachers can't afford to educate effectively whenever they have personal problems related to their salary. After that, without an energetic mood or happy satisfactory income, teachers might not want to educate students, as possibly, they share with only instructions with no additional explained information. Then what might will happen, certainly non-existent educational theories. In current life, the expectancy for living longer and happily also related to the education and learning. In case of that people stand on the same position for a long time, there will be no developmental theories. Association with this point, I have to mention about the bestseller book of Napoleon Hill named 'Think and Grow Rich' which all about money consciousness and success conscious-minded theories. Especially, in Chapter 5, there is given information about Specialized Knowledge, including personal experiences or observations. In purpose of becoming the better one, that anyone can take advantages of these book, in example of sentences: “Knowledge will not attract money, unless it is organized, and intelligently directed, through practical plans of action, to the definite end of accumulation of money. Knowledge is only potential power.” [3] The researchers can understand from this viewpoint that knowledge is the most powerful thing that only human beings can acquire it by reading books. The Brain of the humanity works more intelligently than any wild animals.

In summary, teachers can get demonstrated abilities for working well-paid jobs easily if they have enough experience, critical thinking skills and managing classroom abilities as well as with strong knowledge and mindset. Although this may be true about the salary of teachers should be in higher prices as that they are giving energy to teach young teachers in high schools, especially in pedagogy field.

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